

Schizophrenia: Studying the Influence of Various Factors on the Occurrence and Progression of Disease

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Abstract

Schizophrenia is a mental illness characterized by the breakdown of thought processes and emotional disorders. This disease is characterized by a combination of disorders: cognitive (impaired attention, memory, thinking) and behavioral, productive (hallucinatory, delusional, affective, etc.) and negative (apathy, abulia, emotional and social detachment, etc.) symptoms. Schizophrenia causes psychosis, can be accompanied by disability and negatively affect all areas of life, including personal, social life, family and work activities. This disease is also characterized by changes in emotions, loss of concentration, autism, asociality ("immersion in oneself", unusual thoughts and fantasies), a drop in energy state and a violation of the will. The sick person does not understand that he is ill, and this complicates treatment. Psychoses become more frequent over time and this leads to frequent hallucinations, and they can affect all the senses. The most common are auditory hallucinations in the form of voices and a person's subordination to voices, which can make the situation dangerous. The absence of treatment for schizophrenia leads to an absolute loss of one's own "I", loss of a person's personality, and during an exacerbation of the disease, a person can harm first of all himself and then others. The following research article examines all the factors that can influence the onset and progression of the disease.

Introduction

Schizophrenia is the most common mental disorder that combines positive and negative symptoms, behavioral and mental disorders (memory, attention, thinking, etc.), which entails negative social and economic consequences for patients and their relatives. The diagnosis of "schizophrenia" was introduced in 1908 by the Swiss psychiatrist Eugen Bleuler[4]. The term "schizophrenia" means "split mind" ("schizo" from greek - split, "phren" - soul, mind) [14]. Worldwide, more than 24 million people suffer from schizophrenia. Factors that can influence the development of schizophrenia include genetic predisposition, exposure to viruses, environmental factors, problems during childbirth and psychosocial factors [16].

As mentioned earlier, environmental factors influence the development of schizophrenia spectrum disorders, among which childhood experience plays an important role. Thus, a number of studies have shown that early traumatic experiences of a child (various types of violence and rejection) increase the risk of developing

psychosis and other mental disorders, including affective ones, in the future - years or even decades later. Currently, a number of systems and structures of the brain have been identified that are directly related to the reaction to stress and the formation of schizophrenia spectrum disorders. Thus, child abuse leads to hyperreactivity of the stress response system (hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system), a decrease in the volume of the hippocampus, a decrease in the production of oxytocin and an increase in the production of dopamine, which increases a person's vulnerability to everyday stress and, as a result, the likelihood of psychosis. Stress acts as a trigger that starts, but does not determine the disease process [18]. Schizophrenia is a global health problem and leads to disability affecting all areas of life of patients, including health, work, family relationships, self-realization, etc., characterized by a decrease in social adaptation and the level of social functioning. The disease negatively affects the ability of patients to receive an education, acquire professional skills, which is subsequently associated with a fairly high level of unemployment,

More Information

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which can reach 90% [2]. This disease is characterized by a deficit in the operational type of memory, which does not provide the ability to store and modify the information flow for a long time, and as a result of these false assumptions, scientists suggest the progression of delusional attitudes and false reasoning [1]. This is a severe and often chronic disease that usually first appears in adolescence or early adulthood [7]. Most often observed at the age of 18-35 years [15]. After 50, the onset of the disease is atypical [18]. The patient usually complains of rapid fatigue, loss of strength, enthusiasm and envy, in response to activation, he shows nervousness and capriciousness [15]. Also, the main clinical features of schizophrenia may include delusions, hallucinations, impaired or incoherent thought processes and chains of associations, deficiencies in experiencing appropriate or normal emotions, and withdrawal from reality. A person with schizophrenia may be apathetic and may lack the drive and ability to follow through on a course of action, may withdraw from society, become detached from others, or become preoccupied with bizarre or meaningless fantasies [7].

In particular, disorders of perception, primarily in the form of hallucinations, disrupt the correct attitude of patients to the outside world and can lead to actions that pose a social danger, when derealization occurs (loss of contact with the outside world), fraught with the commission of criminal acts, for example, with frightening, visual hallucinations, attempts at heteroaggression are possible; disorders of thinking in the form of various delusional ideas of an imperative nature can also cause retaliatory aggressive actions against someone (the actor in the patient's delusional experiences), they also do not give the patient the opportunity to usefully use past personal experience; disruption of the anticipatory ability (the ability to foresee the result of one's actions and the course of further events in order to build a "line" of one's behavior in accordance with this without harming one's own interests in the future) excludes correct behavior planning; emotional dullness, apathy often force patients to look for ways to obtain new sensations, often going against accepted social norms, for example, with the use of alcohol; abulia leads to a violation of volitional control of voluntary behavior; a gradual decrease in intelligence makes a patient with schizophrenia more suggestible to others and, as a result, prone to alcoholism and committing antisocial acts: alcohol in such people disinhibits instincts, provoking illegal activity, including in terms of sexual excesses; disorders of consciousness of patients are characterized by varying degrees of detachment from the outside world, cessation of activity and loss of contacts, which can be the cause of a person's helplessness, and he himself becomes a potential

victim of crime under certain circumstances, and disorders of consciousness in the form of hallucinatory experiences are often the cause of socially dangerous acts due to the supposedly existing, but in fact imaginary, need to "defend oneself", "attack", "destroy" and even "kill" [3]. Perception is the basis of higher cognitive functions [13]. Impairment of cognitive functions entails the formation of the disease. D. Kahneman considered several types of cognitive errors: the "hasty conclusion" error, errors in judgment made under the influence of emotions (personalization, dichotomous thinking, selective abstraction, arbitrary conclusions, overgeneralization, catastrophizing), socially conditioned distortions (majority effect, denial of probability, false consensus effect) [10]. Evidence has been obtained of the morphological basis of this disease, showing which zones are involved in the pathological process. Interesting data were discovered during an MRI study of the brain of patients with schizophrenia over time. It turned out that each episode of psychosis causes changes in the brain, and the greatest changes were after the eighth episode of psychosis: significant expansion of the cerebral ventricles and thinning of the gray matter. Currently, much evidence has been accumulated on the presence of signs of neuroinflammation, systemic inflammation and activation of the immune system in patients with schizophrenia [8]. Also, using scanning techniques, it was found that their cerebral cortex has less gray matter and, perhaps most importantly, reduced blood supply to the brain - the theory of hereditary and constitutional predisposition [17].

Clinical insight is usually divided into three subgroups: illness awareness (that is, understanding that unusual and distressing experiences are associated with the illness), symptom recognition (the ability to identify and distinguish specific psychotic symptoms) and awareness of the need for treatment (viewing treatment as a solution to unpleasant experiences) [6]. The goal of the treatment stage is to suppress the positive symptoms of schizophrenia: delusions, microataxia, catatonia and hallucinations [9]. The goals of treatment are the rehabilitation of self-care skills, independent living and the ability to work, as well as the preservation/restoration of the ability to build interpersonal relationships [6]. Patients undergo sessions of various types of psychotherapy. It is necessary to conduct family psychotherapy, which helps to restore harmony in the family, teach the patient's relatives to treat his illness correctly, and the patient to restore emotional ties with family members. Group psychotherapy helps to relearn how to establish social contacts. And individual psychotherapy, therapy with creative self-expression, art therapy, not only helps the patient to better understand what is happening to him, but also allows him to believe in his

own strength and restore the creative potential inherent in a healthy personality [12].

Schizophrenia is characterized by a chronic course with frequent relapses, repeated hospitalizations, decreased quality of life of patients and is usually accompanied by significant psychosocial maladjustment of patients, social isolation and communication difficulties. Each subsequent exacerbation worsens the social functioning of patients, aggravates the prognosis of the disease, increasing the risk of resistance to therapy, which is associated with the growth of neurodegenerative changes in the brain [2]. With each relapse of the disease, the likelihood that the patient will be able to return to the previous level of functioning progressively decreases [5].

An increase in the number of dopamine receptors has also been found in the brain of patients with this disease. A connection has been found between dopamine metabolism disorders and diseases such as schizophrenia, parkinsonism and affective psychoses. This confirms the success of the use of neuroleptic drugs that block dopamine receptors in the treatment of schizophrenia [11]. Therapy and psychosocial support can help people learn social skills, cope with stress, identify early warning signs of relapse, and prolong periods of remission from this disease.[19] Statistically, it has been shown that recovery occurs in 20-30% of cases, and severe cases of the disease are becoming increasingly rare.[14] However, premature death is observed with this disease. The main causes of premature death in people with schizophrenia are cardiovascular, respiratory, and oncological diseases and injuries. Risk factors for the development of these conditions include late detection of oncological pathology, abuse of nicotine, alcohol and drugs, and frequent presence of metabolic syndrome. Also, one of the main causes of death in schizophrenia is suicide.[16]

Literature Review

The most important facts revealed among the series of conducted studies were that patients who are characterized by a high risk of progression of schizophrenia have the results that were found in people with an established diagnosis, as well as a similar set of neurological disorders, although less pronounced, are evidenced by the testimony of close family members of patients with schizophrenia, who are not characterized by psychotic disorders [1].

The theoretical basis of the cognitive model of mental disorders in schizophrenia is the hypothesis that psychotic symptoms (delusions and hallucinations) arise as a result of cognitive errors. It is believed that a life event, which is a trigger, launches a mechanism of distortion of cognitive processes in a predisposed personality, which is expressed in two ways: a violation

of the transfer of past experience to present events and difficulties in controlling intentions and actions. An unstructured flow of sensory information and unrelated material from memory "penetrates" the patient's consciousness, which leads to the emergence of intentions and actions that the person perceives as alien in origin. It is especially emphasized that the disruption of cognitive processes leads to abnormal conscious experiences (for example, neutral actions are perceived as intentional, thoughts seem embedded, a causal connection is established between two unrelated events) [6].

It is also currently believed that changes in the functioning of the dopamine, serotonin, glutamate networks are, if not the cause of schizophrenia, then at least one of the links in its pathogenesis [13].

A set of factors that influence the development of schizophrenia:

- Genetic predisposition;
- Intrauterine, birth or postpartum complications;
- Viral infections of the central nervous system;
- Childhood trauma and neglect of the child's needs.

It can also arise against the background of:

- Severe stress;
- Use of psychoactive substances;
- Presence of phobias and complexes;
- Alcohol dependence [20].

At the present stage, the use of antipsychotic drugs in the treatment of schizophrenia is a key factor in maintaining and supporting the level of social functioning and adaptation in combination with other non-drug rehabilitation methods [2].

Materials and Methods

In accordance with the approaches to considering schizophrenia, to clarify the causes and factors of rapid development of the disease, I chose a quantitative-qualitative approach as the most suitable for studying the course and progression of this disease.

This approach emphasizes the importance of understanding what kind of mental disorder it is, why the number increases from year to year, and what methods of treating this disease are available. Having analyzed and compared studies on schizophrenia, it was revealed that there is an important connection between genetic predisposition and external factors.

The main focus of the study was to determine the influence of stress and mental factors on the progression of schizophrenia in patients, as well as what are the chances of survival. These data can help in optimizing treatment methods and introducing more control over the methods of treating patients and their psychological state.

Empirical Context

The following methods were used to study schizophrenia: clinical observations, psychological and cognitive tests. Their analysis shows the influence of psychological factors on the occurrence and progression of the disease, and systematic observation of patients, including the level of stress, shows us neurological changes in indicators.

In accordance with the purpose of the study, I selected key documents from different countries such as: Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan, etc., as well as scientific sources from the Siberian Bulletin and the Journal of Science in Medicine and Life.

Data Collection

Data has been collected since 2020 by analyzing scientific literature on the influence of genetic and psychological factors on the progression of schizophrenia.

The main research method for studying schizophrenia and its development against the background of neurological changes, as well as the influence of psychological changes, is the analysis of source materials, where studies on the disease were presented and observations of the condition of patients with data on symptoms, results of cognitive impairment and other clinical parameters were studied.

Considering that schizophrenia can be accompanied by a number of other factors, they all have similar characteristics in their impact on the nervous system and the psyche of patients. These factors completely change mental health and bring discomfort to a person, and also completely change his life and the attitude of others towards them, because, as they say, they are now different, they are now sick and they may be haunted by premature death.

Data Analysis

The analysis of strategies in the context of schizophrenia was carried out according to two main parameters: 1) factors that progress the disease and contribute to the cause of premature death; 2) the study of treatment methods by influencing neurological and psychological parameters.

The first aspect of the analysis is to explain that the progression of schizophrenia is associated with a gradual change in neurodegenerative structures in the brain. This then leads to the destruction of cognitive functions, as well as behavioral changes and loss of the ability to perceive reality. Lack of social support, isolation, lack of physical activity and poor nutrition can also have a negative impact on the development of schizophrenia. The second aspect is the treatment of patients using medications to improve cognitive functions, slow down the progression of the disease and improve the quality of life of patients with schizophrenia. Psychological therapy, social activity,

care and support from loved ones can significantly improve the quality of life of patients and slow down the progression of schizophrenia.

The conducted analyses show what this diagnosis is, what is its progression and what factors are present to slow down the progression of schizophrenia.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study proved that the development of schizophrenia is inextricably linked with a gradual deterioration of the brain structure, which leads to a deterioration in the perception of life processes, a decrease in cognitive functions, as well as changes in behavior and self-control abilities.

Summarizing the analysis, social factors such as lack of support, isolation, a psychologically unstable lifestyle and childhood trauma were identified that contribute to the occurrence and acceleration of the progression of schizophrenia.

From an objective point of view, medications alone are not enough for the comprehensive treatment of dementia. Firstly, pharmacological treatments aimed at improving cognitive functions and slowing the progression of the disease have proven to be useful. Secondly, it was studied that psychological treatments, social activity and strong family support significantly improve the quality of life of patients with schizophrenia, as well as eliminate the occurrence of relapses. At the same time, stress, isolation and depression were identified as factors contributing to the acceleration of the progression of the disease. These results demonstrate the importance of a holistic approach to the treatment of schizophrenia, taking into account both the physiological and psychosocial aspects of complex treatment.

Taking into account the results of the study, schizophrenia can be attributed to a number of neurological and neuropsychiatric pathologies. When patients learn about their illness, for which there is no specific treatment, but can only prolong the specified period, they panic even more and themselves fall into depression, not realizing how they are worsening the situation. Based on the above, it is possible to introduce a treatment method by introducing daily communication with patients. It is important to find out the true cause of the disease and work with this problem. If the problem lies in the relationship with loved ones, then introduce family therapy. However, if the problem lies in the patient's personal life and there are such problems as burnout, violence, misperception of events and falling into desperation, then it is necessary to introduce psychotherapy and make them understand the values and wonderful opportunities in life.

Therefore, lived experience is not forgotten, and based on it, you can draw the right conclusions and become stronger.

Conclusion

This study provides answers to the following research statements:

- (1) What is schizophrenia and its causes.
- (2) Different treatment methods and causes of death in this disease.

As previous studies have shown, complete recovery from the disease is possible, but after a while, relapses are observed and each subsequent one will be worse than the previous one. It can be noted that medicine and technology do not stand still and are developing every minute, this entails the implementation of a better recovery. The above factors correspond to one of the key tasks facing science and practice today, which indicates an improvement in the quality of life and a slowdown in the development of the pathological process in patients with this diagnosis.

This article is limited by the fact that the experiment with people was not conducted, but the study contributes to our understanding of schizophrenia and determines effective methods for treating this disease. The results emphasize the need for a multidimensional approach that includes both psychological and environmental factors in the treatment of schizophrenia. By implementing these aspects, healthcare professionals can provide more effective support and improve the quality of life of people with schizophrenia and their families.

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